

THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON COMPANY PERFORMANCE IN FOOD AND BEVERAGE SERVICE INDUSTRY OF MALAYSIA

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Abstract

Company performance is important because it shows the company's ability to achieve high profits, good product quality, market share and good financial results. This cross-sectional study will study the influence of leadership style on company performance in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia. The factors of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style will be studied as the independent variables. Data is collected from 397 respondents via online questionnaires Qualtrics. The data is statistically analyze using SPSS software version 26. In this research study, it is found that there is a significant relationship between company performance and transformational leadership style (p-value=0.038) and transactional leadership style (p-value=0.000). Transactional leadership style is the dominant factors influencing company performance follow by transformational leadership style. This research can help the food and beverage service industry to further understand the factors that influence the company performance and be aware of different leadership behavior and further adopt the leadership style to improve the company performance.

Keywords: Company Performance, Transformational Leadership Style, Transactional Leadership Style, Malaysia.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In Malaysia, food and beverage service are one of the sub-sectors in the service industry and this sub-sector industry is growing rapidly due to the growing demand of consumers (Mahafzah, Aljawarneh, Alomari et. al., 2020). The service sector is one of the important ventures of Malaysia to support the country's economy and thus it has a critical commitment to the gross domestic product of Malaysia (Flanders Investment and Trade, 2020). As per O'Neill (2021), the service industry in Malaysia had contributed 54.78% of Malaysia's GDP in 2020.

Food and beverage service seem to be an important sector for the nation growth because it drives the nation's economic (Alrowwad, Obeidat, Tarhini et. al., 2017). Due to the changes of the current environment in technology and rapid change consumer behavior, the company is facing a lot of challenges and managers or supervisors must have the ability to deal with the

constant change of external environment to ensure the profitability of the company (Orozco, Tarhini, Masa'deh et. al., 2015). Therefore, company performance becomes one of the important topics for all the companies where the managers need to analyze the possible factor that will influence their company performance to come out with the appropriate action to initiate the company performance in terms of financial or non-financial profit (Alrowwad et. al., 2017). This is also reaffirmed by Al Khajeh (2018), company performance is important to analyze because it reflects how well the manager contributes to the management process and growth that helps the company to increase the value, achievement, and core market competitiveness.

In the current competitive business environment, leadership is the most critical factor that influences company performance that directly affects the company's future development either success or failure (Ko and Kang, 2019). According to Bass (1985), leadership affects the company's success and failure over 45% to 65% and different leaders have different leadership styles to motivate and lead their employees to achieve a shared goal. Hence, a study on leadership style as the factors influencing on company performance of food and beverage service industry are valuable to the company. Leadership style has a direct influence on company performance because leadership occasion a major influence on the efficiency of resource allocation and the designation of company's strategies and policies align with the company activities and objectives (Al Khajeh, 2018). Strukan, Nikolic and Sefic (2017) stated the effectiveness and high financial performance of companies are vital for a manager or leader to be adaptive and cooperative to cope with environmental changes. In each company, leaders play an essential role as the right leader with the right leadership style can face the unique challenges and uncertainty (Alrowwad et. al., 2017).

Consequently, this study gathers the employees who are working in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia as subjects to study whether the company performance is affected by the different leadership styles of supervisors or managers. Moreover, this study will further explore the linkage or relationship of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style and company performance that can be a reference to the food and beverage service companies to lead their employees to achieve higher company performance.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Company Performance

Company performance describes the company's ability to achieve high profits, good product quality, market share and good financial results over a period of time (Widodo and Silitonga, 2020). Taouab and Issor (2019) stated that company performance can be seen as a determination on whether the company can meet the stakeholders' needs or goals for its survival in the market. The outcome achievement of the company's performance is influenced by employees with skills and knowledge, technology, equipment, working environment, strategic setting, and process of human interaction in the company (Widarti, Subiyanto, and Pramajaya, 2018). In general, company performance is an overall view of the company that identifies the result and achievement of the company by utilizing the resources owned in the

operation activities (Alrowwad et.al., 2017). This is also reaffirmed by Widodo and Silitonga (2020) that company performance can be considered as the performance or quality of work by a person or group of people that carry out the work duties in the company to reach the higher company achievement.

Different companies are using different measurements on company performance that helps them to identify the strategies and coordinated management process including the company's goal setting, decision making and performance evaluation (Bhasin, 2017). According to Tomic, Tesic, Kuzmanovic et. al. (2018), performance measurement is a fundamental principle of management that has an important link between strategy and management activities such as key performance indicators (KPI) which are critical to the current and future success of the company. However, Balance Scorecard (BSC) also one of the popular financial performance measurements in western and also non-western countries by measuring the financial metrics and non-financial measures on customers, internal process, growth, and learning perspectives (Narkuniene and Ulbinaite, 2018).

2.2 Transformational Leadership Style

Transformational originate from 'transform' that refers to the changes from the beginning state to another (Hijazi, Kasim, and Daud, 2016). Transformational leadership is a style of leader behavior where the leaders encourage and inspire the followers to innovate and create change to exceed the initial performance expectation in order to grow and shape the company's future success (Choi, Kim, and Kang, 2017). Alrowwad et. al. (2017) supported that transformational leadership is a process to forecast the value of employees by developing people to accomplish the laid-out objectives. Many researchers (Purwanto, Bernarto, Asbari et. al., 2020; Berraises and Bchini, 2018; Nidadhavolu, 2018) stated that transformational leadership is the most effective leadership style in the company because transformational leaders are taking the concern to maximize human capabilities and enhance the trust relationship through the influencing of their behavior. This is supported by Hansen and Pihl-Thingvad (2018) that transformational leadership imbued the employees with inspiration, motivation and a collective sense of mission that feel excited and aspiration with the heightened awareness of goal.

2.3 Transactional Leadership Style

Wahyuni, Purwandari and Syah (2019) defined transactional leadership as a result-oriented leadership style that focuses on the basic management process of controlling and organizing by calling on the followers' interests. The main focus of transactional leadership in the company is the lead between leader and employees which allows the employees to meet the needs, reduce the anxiety of completing the task and focus on the company vision (Hoxha, 2019). Transactional leadership is the leadership style that focuses on a leader-subordinates relationship without creating any changes for his or her subordinates (Kalsoom et. al., 2018). This is because the transactional leader is contributing the task to the subordinates according to the general rules and proper management system in the operation process (Adam, Indradewa, and Syah, 2020). Transactional leadership can also consider as reward and punishment-oriented leader where the leaders are concerned about success or failure in completing the task

(Adriansyah, Setiawan, and Yuniarinto, 2019). Furthermore, the transactional leadership style also represents the exchange relationship process where the leaders and employees can negotiate the task for different types of rewards and form a mutual agreement with the employees to keep close the responsibility and expectation to the agreement (Hoxha, 2019).

2.4 Fundamental Theory

The concept of performance is exploited in academic studies to describe the result of the business or operation activities performed by the company’s stakeholders (Narkunienė and Ulbinaitė, 2018). Performance theory is defined as the perceived relationships between different performance dimensions and company performance (Kotane, 2015). Besides, performance theory exists in the minds of individuals that are consciously or subconsciously that will evolve over time (Beer and Micheli, 2018). Performance theory is important for the company as a dimension of the basis for reward, staffing and development of decisions which are implied in current and future performance (Hashim, Che Omar, Hamzah et. al., 2018).

According to Tawas (2019), the performance focuses on the result of its work, which is a universal concept that shows the operational effectiveness of the company and part of the work based on established standards to achieve the desired results. In general, performance theory highlighted the part on how to demonstrate across different works and performance antecedents to combine as performance results (Krausert, 2009). Performance theory proposes the cognitive ability, personal traits and experiences to show a performance-relevant behavior which includes an action taken, decision or cognition that significantly influences how well the organization operates in terms of financial and marketing performance (Hashim et. al., 2018). Performance theory produces outputs as immediate and tangible consequences of behavior then, further influenced by distal context factors such as market conditions to yield intangible and lagging performance outcomes (Joy, Belk, Charters et. al., 2018).

3.0 Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Figure 1 illustrate the theoretical framework and demonstrates the relationship between independent variables and dependent variable. The independent variable includes the transformational leadership style and Transactional Leadership style as the dimension of Yukl

(1989) Leadership Style whereas the dependent variable is company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia.

4.0 Research Methodology

The sample size is a count of the number of sample units that can be utilized for an accurate analysis over a population for data collection (Taherdoost, 2017). According Department of Statistic Malaysia Official Portal (2021) stated that Malaysia had 852,102 employees engaged in the food and beverage service industry, thus the sample size for this research study will be 382 which represent over 75,000 but not more than 1,000,000 population size and 400 questionnaires will be distributed in this research (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). Based on Morris and Rosenbloom (2017), the pilot test is also described as a rehearsal for the research to observe the research approach whether the execution of the entire research is sufficient enough to apply in the research before the real implementation. The pilot test is significant because it determines the feasibility of the study and examines which item should be removed to make sure the accuracy of the constructs in hypothesis testing (Fraser, Fahlman, Arscott et. al., 2018). In this study, the sample size for pilot test must be 10% or 20% of the actual sample size of the study. Based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the sample size for this research study is 382. Thus, there are 40 of the respondents are required to run the pilot test.

Pilot test: Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis (Dependent Variable and Independent Variables)

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test (Dependent Variable)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.725
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	201.236
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test (Independent Variable)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.740
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	314.006
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

KMO Bartlett's test of sphericity provides the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling with the rule of thumbs where the KMO value must be greater than 0.6 (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). Table 2 is the result of the KMO test for Dependent Variable which is 0.725 and table3 shows the result of KMO value for independent variables is 0.740. Both of the KMO values are greater than 0.60 that indicates the sample is adequate and validated to go for further analysis.

Table 4: Factor Loading (Dependent Variable)

Factor Loading for Pilot Test (DV)		
	Initial	Extraction
Our company had achieved a very positive financial outcome	1	.755
We have the higher return on investment that our competitors	1	.665
We are satisfied with our return on sales	1	.700
Our company is growing steadily in the past three years	1	.748
Our customers have the high level of satisfaction toward our company	1	.713
Our company provide better quality service than our competitors do	1	.751

Table 5: Factor Loading (Independent Variable)

Factor Loading for Pilot Test (DV)		
	Initial	Extraction
My supervisor guarantees the investment, resources and support needed for changes and decision making	1	.724
My supervisor empowered followers, boost trust and self-efficacy to sustain performance	1	.639
My supervisor foster innovation thinking among followers in order to enhance the individual and group performance	1	.807
My supervisor has a clear common view of its final aims by encouraging the follower to reflect on past issues in new ways	1	.707
My supervisor is accessible, listen actively and respond the people to promote organizational citizenship behavior and vision to induce the commitment to organizational goal.	1	.800
My supervisor gives the subordinates what they want to exchange for their hard work to achieve company goal	1	.745
My supervisor boosts followers' morale by rewarding individuals with praise or recognition when they performed at or above expectation to improve company performance	1	.565
My supervisor gives positive feedback and show his or her appreciates of subordinates to keep performance aligned with what is expected.	1	.763
My supervisor actively monitors the work of their subordinates, watch for deviations from rules and standard and take corrective action to prevent mistake	1	.857
My supervisor links the goal to rewards, clarify expectation, provide necessary resources and set mutually agreed upon goal for successful performance.	1	.740

According to table 4 and table 5, the majority of factor loading for both dependent and independent variables are above 0.6 that complies with the rule of thumbs. Based on table 5, there is one item in the independent variable that is lower than 0.6. According to Ong and Puteh (2017), the extraction in pilot tests between 0.5 to 0.599 is still acceptable but values lower than 0.5 must be removed. Since all the metrics of 40 sample size values are greater than 0.5, the questionnaire survey does not need to delete any items and all the items are valid and suitable to apply to future analysis.

Table 6: Total Variance Explained (Dependent Variable)

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.333	72.212	72.212	4.333	72.212	72.212
2	.694	11.568	83.779			
3	.499	8.316	92.095			
4	.259	4.309	96.404			
5	.150	2.497	98.901			
6	.066	1.099	100.000			

Table 7: Total Variance Explained (Independent Variable)

Total Variance Explained						
Components	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
1	6.131	61.310	61.310	6.131	61.310	61.310
2	1.214	12.141	73.451	1.214	12.141	73.451
3	.678	6.780	80.232			
4	.612	6.122	86.354			
5	.450	4.496	90.850			
6	.335	3.352	94.202			
7	.226	2.255	96.457			
8	.161	1.612	98.070			
9	.143	1.427	99.497			
10	.050	.503	100.000			

As depicted in table 7, it extracted 2 Eigen values which are also equal to the sum of independent variables in the analysis and table 6 alone extracted 1 Eigen value that is proportional to the amount of dependent variable. Each of the component is meeting the rule of thumbs which are more than 1 (Sekaran and Bougie, 2019). Therefore, the Eigen value greater than 1 and equate with the number of independent variables are acceptable because the independent variable and dependent variable are applying with correlation matrix (Cooper and Schindler, 2018).

Pilot Testing: Reliability Test

Reliability test in SPSS is to test whether the problems were sufficient to generate a positive outcome for future research and ensure the consistency and repeatability data in this research study (Hair et. al., 2019).

Table 8: Reliability Test result for dependent variable and independent variable

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Company Performance	0.922	6
Transformational Leadership Style	0.880	5
Transactional Leadership Style	0.869	5

According to table 8, the dependent variable and independent variables are assumed to be strong because Cronbach's alpha is higher above 0.8. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2019), the reliability test with Cronbach's Alpha more than 0.8 is a very good reliability. In sum, the Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.922 to 0.869 in the table implies that the high reliability of each item in the variable.

5.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Descriptive Analysis

In this research, questionnaires are distributed online to reach the respondents who are working in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia. There are a total of 397 respondents received back that exceed the initial sample size of 382 respondents and therefore deemed acceptable (Krejcie and Morgan, 1970).

Table 9: Demographic profile of respondents

Statements	Options	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Q1: What is your gender?	Male	210	52.9	52.9
	Female	187	47.1	100
	Total	397	100	
Q2: What is your age?	20-29 years old	151	38	38
	30-39 years old	133	33.5	71.5
	40-49 years old	85	21.4	92.9
	50 years old and above	28	7.1	100
	Total	397	100	
Q3: Highest Education level	Primary Education	16	4	4
	Secondary Education	51	12.8	16.9
	Certificate/ Diploma	100	25.2	42.1
	Degree/ Bachelor	188	47.4	89.4
	Master	37	9.3	98.7
	PHD	5	1.3	100
Total	397	100		
Q4: Years of Working Experience?	Less than 2 years	74	18.6	18.6
	2-5	72	18.1	36.8
	6-9	86	21.7	58.4
	10 years and above	165	41.6	100
	Total	397	100	
Q5: Where is your current company located?	Central (Selangor, Kuala Lumpur and Putrajaya)	186	46.9	46.9
	Northern (Perlis, Kedah, Penang and Perak)	78	19.6	66.5
	Southern (Negeri Sembilan, Melaka and Johor)	74	18.6	85.1
	Eastern (Kelantan, Terengganu and Pahang)	31	7.8	92.9
	Sabah/Sarawak	28	7.1	100
	Total	397	100	

The total respondents who participated in this survey were male with 52.9% (n=210) and female was 47.1% (n=187). The majority of respondents were coming from the age band of 20-29 years old (38%) and followed by 30-39 years old (33.5%). The age band of 50 years old and above is the lowest range (7.1%) and respondents in the age of 40-49 years old also contributed to 21.4%. There are 47.4% of respondents' educational level is degree or bachelor and followed by 25.2% is certificate/ diploma and secondary education (12.8%). Only a small portion of the respondents hold PHD (1.3%) and Primary education (4%). Besides, most of the

respondents in this research study had 10 years and above working experience (41.6%), followed by 6-9 years (21.7%) and less than 2 years (18.6%). The working experience of respondents among 2-5 years (18.1%) reached the lowest in this survey. The majority of the respondents are working in central such as Selangor, Kuala Lumpur and Putrajaya that contributed 46.9%. The respondents who are working in Northern is 19.6% and after that is Southern with 18.6%. Respondents who are working in Sabah and Sarawak are the least with 7.1% and Eastern is 7.8%. All the respondents are eligible and literate to understand and fill in the questionnaire as all the 397 respondents are age 18 above and majority is in degree's education level.

5.2 Preliminary Test: Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis (Dependent Variable)

Table 10: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Dependent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.896
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1106.870
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

Table 11: Factor Loading (Dependent Variable)

Factor Loading of Preliminary Test (DV)		
	Initial	Extraction
Our company had achieved a very positive financial outcome	1	.621
We have the higher return on investment that our competitors	1	.624
We are satisfied with our return on sales	1	.642
Our company is growing steadily in the past three years	1	.619
Our customers have the high level of satisfaction toward our company	1	.632
Our company provide better quality service than our competitors do	1	.645

Table 12: Total Variance Explained (Dependent Variable)

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.783	63.052	63.052	3.783	63.052	63.052
2	.594	9.904	72.956			
3	.447	7.453	80.409			
4	.426	7.106	87.515			
5	.398	6.640	94.154			
6	.351	5.846	100.000			

Factor Analysis includes the KMO and Bartlett's test, factor loading and Eigen values. The KMO and Bartlett's test for company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia has a value of 0.896 that indicates in table 10. In table 11, the factor loading for all the items in dependent variable have exceed 0.6, therefore the items are appropriate in this study. In eigen values, the result shows that the items are more than 1 which are considered as relevant and construct to the study (Sekaran and Bougie, 2019). According to the table 12, the first component exceeds 1 and there is total 63.052% of total variance of company performance. In general, the overall KMO and Bartlett's Test, factor loading and Eigen values complies with the minimum criteria and the scale taken on company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia is adequate for this research.

Factor Analysis (Independent Variables)

Table 13: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Independent Variables

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.856
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1852.684
	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Table 14: Factor Loading (Independent Variables)

Factor Loading of Preliminary Test (DV)		
	Initial	Extraction
My supervisor guarantees the investment, resources and support needed for changes and decision making	1	.655
My supervisor empowered followers, boast trust and self-efficacy to sustain performance	1	.602
My supervisor foster innovation thinking among followers in order to enhance the individual and group performance	1	.638
My supervisor has a clear common view of its final aims by encouraging the follower to reflect on past issues in new ways	1	.664
My supervisor is accessible, listen actively and respond the people to promote organizational citizenship behavior and vision to induce the commitment to organizational goal.	1	.620
My supervisor gives the subordinates what they want to exchange for their hard work to achieve company goal	1	.626
My supervisor boosts followers' morale by rewarding individuals with praise or recognition when they performed at or above expectation to improve company performance	1	.607
My supervisor gives positive feedback and show his or her appreciates of subordinates to keep performance aligned with what is expected.	1	.643
My supervisor actively monitors the work of their subordinates, watch for deviations from rules and standard and take corrective action to prevent mistake	1	.637
My supervisor links the goal to rewards, clarify expectation, provide necessary resources and set mutually agreed upon goal for successful performance.	1	.630

Table 15: Total Variance Explained (Independent Variables)

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.819	48.192	48.192	4.819	48.192	48.192
2	1.502	15.022	63.214	1.502	15.022	63.214
3	.756	7.560	70.775			
4	.622	6.219	76.993			
5	.542	5.415	82.409			
6	.452	4.516	86.925			
7	.404	4.038	90.963			
8	.351	3.507	94.470			
9	.315	3.146	97.616			
10	.238	2.384	100.000			

As shown in Table 13, the KMO and Bartlett’s test of sphericity shows a value of 0.856 which is greater than 0.6 and closer to 1. This shows that the items in the questionnaire for independent variables are statistically relevant correlation (Cooper and Schindler, 2018). Besides, table 14 shows all the factor loading for independent variables have the value more than 0.6 that indicates that the factors have sufficient variance in this study. Based on Table 15, the Eigen values for independent variables are also acceptable. There are two components that have Eigen values of more than 1 that equal to the two independent variables in the research. Thus, it can be concluded that the data can proceed further to run the reliability test in the following section.

Preliminary Test: Reliability Test

Table 16: Reliability Test on Dependent Variable and Independent Variables

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	No of Items
Company Performance	.883	6
Transformational Leadership Style	.856	5
Transactional Leadership Style	.852	5

As the result shown in Table 16, all the items in questionnaire for dependent and independent variables are above 0.8 that indicates that a very good reliability and standard consistency (Cooper and Schindler, 2018). All the independent variables are of good consistency that reveals that all the 16 items tested agree with the rule of thumb and are suitable for future study.

5.3 Multiple Regression Analysis (Hypothesis Testing)

Hypothesis testing is to determine whether the statement is correct, and model fit with the current study between the dependent variable and the independent variables (Sekaran and Bougie, 2019). Below show the hypotheses in this research study:

H1: Transformational Leadership Style as a dimension of Yukl (1989) Leadership Style has a significant influence on company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia.

H2: Transactional Leadership Style as a dimension of Yukl (1989) Leadership Style has a significant influence on company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia.

Table 17: Multiple Regression Model Summaries

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.661 ^a	.437	.435	2.02899	1.381
a. Predictors: (Constant), Transactional, Transformational					
b. Dependent Variable: C Ptotal					

As shown in Table 17, the results identified transformational and transactional are significantly correlated with the influence on company performance as the correlation coefficient is ($r=0.661$). The R-squared value is 0.437 that representing 43.7% of total variance influencing the company performance in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2019), the value of R-square in the model summary should be greater than 0.4 to nearer 1 that can just be considered the model is fit. Thus, the model is fit for the study because the R- square reached the minimum value of 0.4 (Ahmad and Ejaz, 2019). Besides, the value of Durbin-Watson is 1.381 (Hair et. al., 2019). If the value of Durbin-Watson does not reach approximately 2 or within the acceptance range of 1.5 to 2.5, the residual is not correlated. In sum, there is minimal autocorrelation since the value is between 0 to 4 which is 1.381.

Table 18: ANOVA

ANOVA						
Model	Sum of Squares	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1260.869	2	630.434	153.138	.000
	Residual	1622.013	394	4.117		
	Total	2882.882	396			

Based on Table 18, the F-value for the dependent variable and two independent variables is 153.138. Field (2017) stated that the p-value must be less than 0.05 at 95% of confidence level to identify whether the data is a significant fit to the model. The P-value of Table 19 is 0.000 that shows the value meets the rule of thumb which is required to be <0.05 . In conclusion, the independent variables in this research are accepted and the model is fit.

Table19: Results of Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Co linearity Statistic		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	7.854	1.191		6.596	.000		
	Transformational	.114	.055	.092	2.080	0.038	0.722	1.384
	Transactional	.729	.053	.608	13.673	0.000	0.722	1.384
a. Dependent Variable: C Ptotal								
b. Independent Variable: Transformational, Transactional								

According to Cooper and Schindler (2018), the P-value of all the variables must be <0.05 to meet the rule of thumbs in order to support the model. Upon evaluating Table 20, the result shows the analysis transformational leadership style (P-value=0.038, significant at 0.05 level) and transactional leadership style (P-value= 0.000, significant at 0.05 level). Transactional leadership style has the dominant effect on influencing the company performance where the Beta Coefficient is 0.729 and followed by transformational leadership style (0.114). Therefore, all the variables in this research study have a positive influence on company performance in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia (Ahmad and Ejaz, 2019). In Table19, the result shows there was no multicollinearity of variables due to the VIF values being less than 10. Besides, the rule of thumbs of tolerance value in multicollinearity analysis must be greater than 0.1 (Daoud, 2017). The tolerance value of both independent variables is exceeded 0.1 where the transformational leadership style (0.722) and transactional leadership style (0.722).

The resultant equation from the analysis is as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia} \\ &= 7.854 + 0.114 (\text{Transformational Leadership Style}) + 0.729 (\text{Transactional Leadership Style}) \end{aligned}$$

In sum, the transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style increase by 1 unit, the company performance is expected to rise by 0.114 and 0.729 on average. Based on the result, transactional leadership style has the highest influence on company performance in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia with 0.729 and then followed by transformational leadership style.

6.0 Summary of Findings

All the hypotheses are accepted in this research study that is shown in the below table. Therefore, it can be concluded that the factor of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style and company performance in the food and beverage service industry of Malaysia has a significant positive relationship.

Table 20: Status of Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses	Status
H1: Transformational Leadership Style as a dimension of Yukl (1989) Leadership Style has a significant influence on company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia.	Accepted
H2: Transactional Leadership Style as a dimension of Yukl (1989) Leadership Style has a significant influence on company performance in food and beverage service industry of Malaysia.	Accepted

7.0 CONCLUSION

In this research, transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style had a significant positive relationship toward company performance. The dominant influence of the transactional leadership style on company performance has the highest influencing power on company performance. Transactional leadership is characterized by contingency rewards where the leader or manager is giving the reward in exchange for effort and good performance. Food and beverage service companies of Malaysia are suggesting paying high attention to the employees' low-level needs and excite their employees on what they can exchange once they complete the goal. Consequently, the company must focus on the latest information on the compensation package by doing market research to design a set of compensation that meets the needs of employees. Lastly, transformational leadership style is also a potential factor that influences company performance because it introduces the changes identifies a clear vision and focuses on the future long-term plan. Hence, the suggestion for the food and beverage service company is to promote the existence development of transformational managers to increase company performance. The implementation of proper training for transformational development can focus on providing learning on how to communicate the high expectation and how to motivate their followers with extra effort and articulate shared goals. In a nutshell, company performance is influenced by the factor of transformational leadership style and transactional leadership style and it is recommended future researchers further explore other possible factors to enhance the academic knowledge and improve the company performance of food and beverage service.

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